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THE EFFECTS OF SURFACE IRRIGATION TECHNOLOGY ON THE YIELD OF INTENSIVE APPLE ORCHARDS

Sarimsakov M.M.

Bukhara Institute of Natural Resources Management at the National Research University Tashkent Institute of Irrigation Engineers and Agricultural Mechanization, Candidate of Agricultural Sciences, Senior Research. Bukhara, Uzbekistan.

E_mail: ingenering67@gmail.com , phone: (+998 90) 968-65-24,

ORCID 0000-0003-0192-8532

Annotation. *Irrigation erosion is a process that has a major negative impact on agricultural production, which greatly reduces soil fertility and crop yields. Costs related to crop production will increase. Today in the country more than 720 thousand hectares of irrigated areas are subject to irrigation erosion. According to the results of scientific researches, in typical gray soils with slopes of more than 0,3⁰, during the season, 24.6 tons of soil particles were washed away from each hectare of land under normal irrigation of soil particles by 6-12% when irrigated using transverse furrow furrows. Reduction of soil moisture depth to 0.8 m during irrigation will save 10-15%.*

Keywords; *intensive apple orchard, fruit tree, apple, irrigation methods, soil moistening depth, irrigation erosion, soil particles, turbidity, apple yield.*

Introduction: Implementation of the tasks set in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 27, 2017, No PP-3405 "On the Development of Irrigation and Reclamation of Irrigated Lands for 2018-2019". According to the "Strategy of action on five priority directions of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" approved by the Decree No. 4947 of the President further improvement of irrigated lands, development of network of melioration and irrigation facilities, introduction of intensive methods of agriculture, first of all modern water-saving technologies, global climate change and the Aral Sea crisis. Extensive efforts are being made to implement systemic measures to mitigate its impact.

Implementation of this resolution and the tasks outlined in the "State Program" is one of the main tasks of every leader, scientist and specialist.

At present, large-scale work on intensive gardening, the introduction of advanced and economical technologies in agriculture, the intensive development of industries is being carried out in our country.

Scientific researches on the implementation of agricultural crops on irrigated land with optimal water standards, methods and procedures of irrigation, taking into account climatic conditions, soil type, mechanical composition, reclamation and geological and hydrogeological conditions of the world: Austria, USA, Canada, Israel, China, India and other countries and their research centers, universities, United States Department of Agriculture (USDA), Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), Colorado State University, California University Institute of Business and Irrigation (USA), Institute of Cotton Research (ICR, CAAS), Shekhazi University (China), Stockholm Technology University (Sweden), International Water Management Institute (IWMI), (Shrilanka), Australian Cotton Research Institute (Australia), Indian Agricultural Research Institute (India), International Organization for Grapes and Wine (IOGW) [3,4,5,7,8,13,11,12,16,17,19].

Noteworthy are the research and development of such scientists as S.F. Averyanov, N.D. Kremenetsky, B.A. Shumakov, Stanley Kindson, M.A. Sharov, G.K. Lgov, N.N. Ivanov, N. V. Danilchenkova, M.S. Grigorov, V.P. Popova, A.S. Ovchinnikov on the development of water-saving technologies in conditions of water shortage.

An extensive research has been carried out by scientists such as T.Forrest, H.Ferenco, R.Harald, D.K.Kindsaid, N.R.Khamraev, B.F. Kambarov, V.A. Dukhovnyy, V.I. Sokolov, F.N. Rahimboev, N.F. Bepalov, S.Ch. Djalalov, K.M. Mirzajanov, Sh.Nurmatov, G.A. Bezborodov, A.E. Avliyokulov, M.H. Hamidov, R.K. Ikromov, F.A. Baraev, B.S. Serikbaev, A.T. Salohiddinov, A.A. Ramazonov, E.J. Makhmudov, B. Mambetnazarov, G. Yuldashev, B.S. Komilov, Yu. Esanbekov, A. Isashev, K. Isaboev, B. Matyakubov, S. Isaev and many others on agricultural irrigation, efficient use of water resources, improvement of existing irrigation methods and increasing the efficiency of new technologies.

Agriculture is an important sector of Uzbekistan, accounting for 32% of employment. It is also the main source of income for rural areas. It should be noted that 49% of the population lives in rural areas. If you look at the media, today Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan are among the most wasteful countries in the world. For example, Turkmenistan's per capita water use is 5,500 cubic meters per year. If you compare this indicator with the developed countries, it is 4 times higher than the USA and 13 times more than in China [13].

Problem: More than 90% of the country's water resources are used for irrigation. The bulk (80-83%) of this amount falls on the growing season. During the period of the novelties, water is used for irrigation of fall crops, wet harvesting and pre-planting irrigation, and salinization of saline soils. About 70% of irrigated land is pumped. In irrigated agriculture, the amount of water consumption varies, depending on natural conditions, the technical condition of irrigation systems, and the methods

and techniques used. Therefore, the average country water consumption is 14,000 m³/ha, while in areas with poor irrigation systems this figure is 16-18 thousand m³/ha.

This is not the only problem facing agriculture in the country, in addition, the effects of wind and irrigation erosion on irrigated areas are contributing to a decrease in soil fertility, a key factor that ensures sustainable crop yields from cultivated crops.

According to the information of our mature scientists, who conducted scientific research in this regard, today more than 722,000 hectares of irrigation areas of the Republic’s existing irrigated areas, about 1812,000 hectares of which are wind, more than 1929,000 hectares are damaged by water and wind erosion processes. (K.Mirzajonov, Sh. Nurmatov, 1986,.. 2005) [2,3,5,9,12,16].

Scientific researches: Justification of irrigation methods in cultivation of intensive apple orchards, determination of irrigation rules and norms, study of soil type, mechanical composition, geological and hydrogeological conditions, soil moisture and other factors influence on intensive gardens, irrigation methods, techniques and techniques for soil conditions. The development of the technology in the conditions of typical sandy soils of Tashkent region. In the gardens, the experiments were mainly conducted to improve soil irrigation methods, reduce irrigation erosion processes, and determine the effect of optimum soil moisture depth on water consumption, erosion processes, and apple productivity.

This experiment was conducted by the “Kibray Agro Impeks” farm, which has relatively high slopes and is affected by irrigation erosion during crop irrigation.

The scientific works of scientists V.B. Gussak, L.I. Prosalov, D.L. Armand, V.O. Pastushenko, V.V. Zvonkov, K.L. Khalupyak, A.K. Shikula, A.M. Gordeev, M.N. Zaslavsky, I.A. Skachkov, P.S. Tregubov, Ch.P. Surmach, X.S. Romanov, V.A. Belyaev, K. Alekperov, , F.A. Mironchenko, K.A. Zelensky, X.M. Makhsudov, V.A. Malinkin, K.M. Mirzajonov, Sh.N. Nurmatov, Sh. Kholmatova are important in the development of the causes, distribution and measures of water erosion that can reduce soil fertility . [2,3,4,5,6,9,10,11,12].

According to the data provided by M.P. Mednis, K.M. Mirzajonov, S.S. Maylibaev and others, the washing of soil particles starts at a slope of 0,5⁰. Water erosion occurs mainly in areas with slopes.

According to K.M. Mirzajonov, N.N. Besedin, Sh.N. Nurmatov (1995, 2005) the level of soil washing depends on the amount of nutrients contained in it, the agro-technical condition (crop rotation), irrigation period and many other factors. According to the authors, on typical sandy soils of Tashkent region, the slope was 0,5⁰, during the cotton period of the cotton was 45 tons per hectare and 44,7 tons at 0,3⁰ [9,11].

Results of research: Methods of intensive apple orchards irrigation in the field of pre-irrigated mountainous areas of the Tashkent region (The “Kibray Agro

Impeks” plantation and horticultural farm) with moderate and heavy sandy loam typical loamy soils optimal soil moisture depth, rates and timing of irrigation, and their influence on the agrophysical properties of soil, erosion processes and fruit yields were determined.

Irrigation was conducted using straight and transverse furrows with 75-80-70% of the soil moisture content in the order of ultimate field moisture capacity, which determined the optimal soil moisture depth and the amount of water and duration of irrigation. In the control variant, the pre-irrigation soil moisture content was 70-70-65% against the ultimate field moisture capacity.

In order to substantiate the optimal moisture depth of the soil, moisture content of 1.0 m, 0.8 m and 0.5 m was provided to the soil, and the effect of optimal soil moisture washing, water consumption, and productivity were investigated.

At the same time, irrigation methods were used, namely, furrows with transverse fences instead of straight furrows (Sh. Nurmatov, 2002), which allowed minimizing the amount of water supplied to furrows and reducing runoff [9].

Water samples from all furrows were collected 5, 30, 45, and 60 minutes before the flow of water flow and before the end of irrigation, in order to determine the amount of soil particles (mud) that was washed away with wastewater in the experimental area. (one liter). In determining the amount of turbidity in the samples taken, the bottled water was suspended for several days and the sludge was removed from the sediment and weighed [2].

Each irrigation determined the amount of soil particles that were washed away with sewage, and the total amount of soil particles that washed out during the growing season.

In areas where the irrigated area has a slope (≥ 0.30), erosion processes have a significant negative impact on soil fertility.

In our research, irrigation was carried out 5-8 times depending on the soil moisture depth during the growing season, and the irrigation rates were 300-700 m³/ha, and the seasonal irrigation rates were 1980-2580 m³/ha (Table 1).

The control version of the experiment, namely irrigation of 1 m layer of soil using simple furrows, irrigation rates are 620-680 m³/ha, seasonal water consumption is 2582 m³/ha, transverse furrows with 1 m layer of soil. In Option 2, where irrigation was carried out, the number of irrigation was increased 6 times, the seasonal irrigation rate was 2447 m³/ha, irrigation was carried out from a transverse barrier furrow, and the soil was watered with 0.8 m of soil. seasonal watering rate was 2187 m³/ha, and watering 0.5 m of soil was carried out 8 times of irrigation, and seasonal water consumption was 1983 m³/ha. As a result of reduction of soil moisture depth and irrigation using transverse furrows, it was possible to save 20.5-26.1% of irrigation water per control option.

Table 1.**Influence of irrigation techniques elements on water consumption (m³/ha) and washing of soil particles (t/ha)**

Variants	Soil moistening	Seasonal water consumption, (m ³ /ha)	Economized water, amount, at %	Washed soil, t/ha	Apple tree productivity, c/ha	Difference, ±
1-var. supervise	1,0	2582	-	-	23.4	
2-var.	1,0	2447	135	5.23	29.0	+5.6
3-var.	0,8	2187	395	15.3	30.7	+7.3
4-var.	0,5	1983	599	23.2	24.8	+1,4

The first (control) version of the experiment, namely, 1.0 m of soil in normal furrows, is provided with moisture and during irrigation, the amount of soil particles that is washed with sewage averaged 29.0 t/ha, providing this layer of soil moisture.

When investigating the effect of the applied technologies on fruit yields, it was found that the increase of soil moisture depth to a certain extent influenced the growth and productivity of trees.

Option 1 of the experiment, that is, when 1.0 m of soil was moistened and irrigated using ordinary furrows, the yield was 23.4 t/ha, while the same moisture supply was used in the second irrigated furrows. The productivity was 29.0 t/ha. The main reason for this is that when irrigation is done using transverse furrows, water discharge is reduced and the amount of water absorbed in the soil increases. This, in turn, has provided the plant with good moisture content.

Variants 3 and 4 of our experiments were found to have higher yields (30.7 t/ha) with the moisture content of 0.8 and 0.5 m layers of soil using transverse furrow furrows. It is also important to note that in typical gray soils with deep groundwater below 5 m, setting the moisture depth by 0.5 m resulted in a decrease in apple productivity (24.8 t/ha) (Graph 1).

Conclusions: Reduction of soil moisture depth in the maintenance of intensive orchards in the conditions of typical wet soils that are prone to irrigation erosion and the use of transverse furrow furrows for irrigation, saving irrigation water by 5.23-23.2%, as well as reducing erosion of soil particles allow by 6.0-31.2%.

In typical gray soils with deep groundwater (below 5 m) irrigation of intensive orchards with moisture content of 0.80 m of soil in the order of 75-80-70% of the ChDNS is qualitative and economical. Provides high (30.7 t/ha) apple crop. This is

6.9 t/ha higher than the control variant and 1.7-5.9 t/ha higher than the variants irrigated using transverse furrow furrows, providing 1.0 m and 0.5 m of soil with moisture.

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